

Academic Stress and Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Public Colleges of Education in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined academic stress and the academic performance of business education students in colleges of education in Lagos State, Nigeria. Three research questions and corresponding research hypotheses were formulated. The population of the study comprised 1850 full-time business education students studying in the three public colleges of education in Lagos State. A sample of 270 respondents was selected using simple random sampling technique. The Stress and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ) was used to collect relevant data. Out of the 270 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed, only 259 copies met criteria for data analysis, representing 95.9% return rate. Eleven copies of questionnaire returned were discarded for incomplete filling out; the remaining 259 copies were utilized for the study. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study discovered that academic stress did not significantly impact students academic performance in public colleges of education in Lagos State. The study also discovered that there is statistically significant difference in academic performance between business education students who use different stress management strategies in public college of education in Lagos State. One of the recommendations given is that counseling centers should be instituted in the respective colleges of education and they should place more attention and support on counseling and training students to effectively manage and cope with stress.

Keywords: Academic Stress, Academic Performance, Business Education Student, College of Education, Lagos State

Introduction

Stress is an unavoidable part of the normal fabrics of human existence. Every individual experiences stress irrespective of age, occupation, social status, race, or cultural background. Stress is a psychophysiological process that generates a host of chemical and hormonal reaction in the body (Dhanalakshmi & Murty, 2020). Stress is the body's way of responding to any kind of demand or threat. Consequently, the World Health Organization became alarmed and classified stress as the health epidemic of the 21st century (Fink, 2017). High levels of stress is associated with poor academic performance (Sohail, 2013), while low stress however, may not necessarily result in good performance as under the circumstances, if tasks are too easy, some students may find them unchallenging and become bored, which can ultimately lead to poor academic performance (Uchil, 2017). Stress affects students learning and academic performance negatively as it can lead to anxiety, sleep problems and interpersonal conflicts (Sohail, 2013). Majority of students with stress reported poor self-esteem and high depression (Baste & Gadkari, 2014). The business education students go through the same ordeal daily in their academic quest.

Business education students are future torch bearers of the education system and the business world; they are trained to major in both theory and pedagogy of teaching; and also in business administration. Business education students are faced with enormous workload which comprises educational courses on one hand and also business courses (Obiete, Nwazor, & Vin-Mbah, 2015). Obiete et al, (2015) saw business education as a dynamic field of study geared towards preparing youths and adults for a career in business, that is, for actual practice in the world of business. Business education also educates students about business by preparing youths and adults for intelligent and effective consumption of economic goods and services offered to society in this free enterprise economy. Business education students in the colleges of education offer so many courses per semester, which comprises of core business courses and educational courses. This is aimed at ensuring that the graduates are sound in theory and practice, and have the capacity and capability to compete favourably with their counterparts. College of Education is the unit of tertiary education in Nigeria saddled with the responsibility of training teachers to obtain non-degree but qualitative professional certificate in education called Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). The origin of Colleges of Education in Nigeria dates back to the 1950s. In the report of Ashby Commission of 1959, it is evident that there was a need to provide middle level manpower to meet Nigerian needs in the area of teaching manpower; hence college of education was set up to produce seasoned teachers who are equipped with the theory and pedagogy of teaching. In recent years, college education has become highly competitive and demanding. As a result, College students are under both internal and external pressure, which creates stress and anxiety. There are numerous external pressures such as family, especially parents, who put high demands and expectations on their child, or financial external pressure, housing, social life, teacher interaction, academic work, etc. These influences can be overwhelming and can cause anxiety and stress (Yikeal, Tareke and

Karvinen 2018). Hence, higher institution students are under a higher amount of stress than individuals who are not attending a tertiary institution.

According to Yikeal et al (2018), college students undergo numerous educational, social, environmental and psychological adjustment difficulties in the new campus atmosphere which may affect their psychosocial well-being and academic performance.

Academic performance according to York, Gibson, and Rankin (2015) is believed to possess an amorphous nature, since it broadly incorporates various factors ranging from attaining a professional degree to the development of students in the moral sense. Academic achievement, academic performance, and learning outcomes are terms often defined and interpreted differently by educational researchers leading to confusion and inconsistencies in their usage (Kumar, Agarwal, & Agarwal, 2021). Academic achievement, academic performance, and learning outcomes are all interpreted differently by educational investigators and require clarification. Therefore, it is difficult to understand each term as they may be explained variously in researches. As the definition of academic performance needs to be clear and not ambiguous, this study follows the specification of Yusuf, Onifade and Bello (2016) who have interpreted performance as “the quantifiable and apparent behavior of a student within a definite period”. This refers to the extent to which a student achieves their educational goals typically measured through grades, test scores and overall engagement in learning activities. Academic performance can be measured by students’ scores; therefore, grade point average and cumulative grade point average are both often used as measurable indicators of academic performance, which were utilised in this study.

Siraj et al. (2014) explored the association between stress levels and the academic performances and demonstrated that respondents with a high and severe stress level were observed to have a higher cumulative grade point average. The medical students were found to be highly capable of managing their stress well and, thus, deny the adverse effect of stress on their academic performance. On the other hand, other studies found no statistically significant relationship between stress and academic performance (Azila-Gbettor et al., 2015). Sohail (2013) conducted a study to determine the relationship of stress and academic performance in first year medical students and to identify sources of stress, levels of stress and relevant coping strategies. The results also show that higher level of stress is associated with poor academic performance.

Stress management is conceptualised in this work as the process of managing demands that are appraised as tasking or exceeding the resource of the person. Stress needs to be controlled in order to minimize its impact on the academic achievement of students and such mechanism can be referred to as management strategy. There are various strategies that can be adopted to control stress such that it can reduce its influence on the academic achievement of students. Researchers have identified strategies that can help students deal with their academic stress. 1. Eat well. 2.

Exercise. 3. Sleep well at night. 4. Don't use drugs, alcohol, or tobacco. 5. Set realistic goals for yourself. 6. Learn stress management skills, such as relaxation techniques and problem solving. 7. Do not over-schedule activities. 8. Find time to relax. 9. Keep a schedule. 10. Get organized. 11. be optimistic and 12. Build resiliency (Omosidi and Jamiu 2019, Sohail 2013). Omosidi and Jamiu (2019), in their study observed that there was a positive significant relationship between relaxation management strategies, lifestyle management strategies, meditation management strategies and academic performance of undergraduates.

The Statement of the Problem

Business education students in colleges of education often face numerous academic challenges that can lead to stress, which in turn can negatively impact their academic performance. The researcher had observed episodes of ill – health, depression, lack of concentration, suicidal tendencies and confusion among college of education students where she teach. Particularly, the researcher had witnessed students fainting and collapsing before and during semester examinations. Most times they are rushed to the hospital for admission and medical care, leaving them mentally and psychologically stressed to concentrate in their studies and write exams.

Moreover, the courses offered by students of business education in colleges of education are enormous when compared to their counterparts studying the same course in the University.

Students of business education are vulnerable to problems associated with personal, social and academic domains. Too often much emphasis is placed on the acquisition of knowledge and academic achievement while neglecting the emotions or feelings of students as they learn. These invariably lead to stress and consequently poor academic performance among other negative results. A lot of reasons has been adduced for students poor performance; like the nonseriousness of the students, teaching methods adopted, learning style, non-utilisation of instructional materials, and audio visual aid, school plant factors, misplaced priority and so on.

In view of these, it would be beneficial to the field of education, as well as Colleges of Education, to find out whether stress is a determinant of academic performance of business education students in public colleges of education in Lagos State.

Objectives

1. To determine whether there is a significant relationship between academic stress and academic performance of business education students as measured by CGPA.
2. To examine how stress management strategies impacts the academic performance of business education students in colleges of education in Lagos state

3. To determine the differences in academic stress levels among business education students in the three colleges of education in Lagos state.

Hypotheses

1. Academic stress does not significantly differ to business education students academic performance(CGPA)
2. Stress Management Strategy does not significantly differ to academic performance (CGPA) of business education students
3. To what extent does Academic Stress level differs among respondents in the three Colleges of education?

Methodology

The current study utilized a quantitative, non-experimental, cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study comprised 1850 students in public colleges of education in Lagos State, Nigeria. The public Colleges of Education in Lagos State are Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka (FCET), Adeniran Ogunsanya College of Education Ijanikin (AOCED), and Michael Otedola College of Primary Education Epe, Lagos (MOCPED). The sample for the study was selected through simple random sampling. Simple random sampling, (hat and draw method) was used to select a total of 270 students, who constituted the sample for the study. An instrument titled Stress and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ) was used to collect relevant data from the respondents. A 4-point rating was adapted. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The face validity was used to ensure that the SAPQ contain the necessary features of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was reviewed by two experts to ensure it measures what it's supposed to. They checked if the questions were clear, concise, and relevant to the research topic. The content validity was aimed at ensuring that the statements raised in the SAPQ aligned with the purpose which it is designed to measure. They verified that the questionnaire covered all relevant aspects of the research topic. Test retest reliability was used to ensure stability of the questionnaire before the main study. A high reliability coefficient of 0.06 indicated that the instrument was reliable and this was considered before proceeding for the main study. The instrument was administered to the participants with the help of two research assistants. The data collected were checked for completeness. Out of the 270 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed, only 259 copies were returned representing 95.9% return rate. Eleven copies of questionnaire returned were discarded for incomplete filling out; the remaining 259 copies were utilized for the study. The information was coded on the computer using Special Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) batch system. The result was used to analyse the hypothesis using analysis of variance ANOVA.

Results

Analysis of personal information

CGPA of respondents

CGPA	Frequency	percent
1.5-2.5	62	24.0
2.5-3.5	106	41.0
Total	259	100

Hypothesis 1: Academic Stress does not significantly differ due to student's academic performance (CGPA).

Table 1

Descriptive and Inferential Analysis on Academic Stress and CGPA

CGPA	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
3.5-4.5	91	50.90	7.69
2.5-3.5	106	47.94	7.48
1.5-2.5	62	53.35	8.15
Total	259	50.28	7.98

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1200.021	2	600.010	10.074	.000
Within Groups	15247.964	256	59.562		
Total	16447.985	258			

Significant at 0.05; $F(2, 256) = 3.03$

The descriptive analysis from Table 1 shows that CGPA group with 1.5-2.5 had the highest mean of 53.35, followed by 3.5-4.5 with the mean of 50.9. The CGPA group with 2.5-3.5 had the least mean of 47.94. An analysis of variance was computed to determine if the mean differences were significant. An F-calculated value of 10.074 was derived. This value was greater than the critical value of 3.03 given 2 and 256 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that Academic Stress significantly differ due to respondents' Cumulative Grade Point Average.

Based on the significant F-value obtained, a Post-Hoc analysis was done using Least Square Difference (LSD) to determine which the pair with the difference. The result of the analysis was presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Post-Hoc analysis showing Pairwise Comparison between Academic Stress and CGPA

(I) Cumulative Grade (J) Point Average	Cumulative Grade Point Average	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
3.5-4.5	2.5-3.5	2.95770*	.008
	1.5-2.5	-2.45374	.055
2.5-3.5	3.5-4.5	-2.95770*	.008
	1.5-2.5	-5.41144*	.000
1.5-2.5	3.5-4.5	2.45374	.055
	2.5-3.5	5.41144*	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

It was observed that the participants in CGPA group with 3.5-4.5 was significant when compare with their counterparts in 2.5-3.5 ($p < 0.05$; $t = 2.96$). Also, the pair of 1.5-2.5 and 2.5-3.5 ($p < 0.05$; $t = 5.41$) was found to be significant.

Hypothesis 2: Stress Management Strategy does not significantly differ to academic performance (CGPA) of business education students

Table 3

Descriptive and Inferential Analysis on Stress Management Strategy and CGPA

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
3.5-4.5	91	25.55	7.11
2.5-3.5	106	22.35	6.19
1.5-2.5	62	21.06	7.87
Total	259	23.17	7.16

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	861.507	2	430.753	8.926	.000
Within Groups	12354.354	256	48.259		
Total	13215.861	258			

Figures from Table 3 show the mean for respondents with CGPA group with 3.5-4.5, 2.5-3.5 and 1.5-2.5 as 25.55, 22.35 and 21.06 respectively. In order to determine the significance of the mean, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was computed. The computation led to F-calculated value of 8.926 as the effect of time management stress on CGPA categories. This computed value was observed to be greater than the critical value of 3.03 given 2 and 256 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that stress management strategy significantly differs due to respondents' Cumulative Grade Point Average.

Based on the significant F-value obtained, a Post-Hoc analysis was done using Least Square Difference (LSD) to determine the pair with the difference. The result of the analysis was presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Post-Hoc analysis showing Pairwise Comparison between Stress Management Strategy and CGPA

(I) Cumulative Grade Point Average	(J) Cumulative Grade Point Average	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
3.5-4.5	2.5-3.5	3.20039*	.001
	1.5-2.5	4.48493*	.000
2.5-3.5	3.5-4.5	-3.20039*	.001
	1.5-2.5	1.28454	.249
1.5-2.5	3.5-4.5	-4.48493*	.000
	2.5-3.5	-1.28454	.249

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

It was observed that the participants in CGPA group with 3.5-4.5 was significant when compare with their counterparts in 2.5-3.5 ($p < 0.05$; $t = 3.2$). Besides, the pair of 3.5-4.5 and 1.5-2.5 ($p < 0.05$; $t = 4.48$) was found to be significant.

Hypothesis 3: Academic Stress does not significantly differ among respondents in the three Colleges.

Table 5
Descriptive and Inferential Analysis on Academic Stress among Colleges

College	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
College A	86	49.38	7.53
College B	93	51.39	8.78
College C	80	49.95	7.41
Total	259	50.28	7.98

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	191.783	2	95.891	1.510	.223
Within Groups	16256.202	256	63.501		
Total	16447.985	258			

Not Significant at 0.05; $F(2,256) = 3.03$

Figures from Table 5 shows that College B, C and A in descending order had mean of 51.39, 49.95 and 49.38 respectively. Furthermore, an analysis of variance was computed to determine if the mean differences were significant. A F-calculated value of 1.51 was derived as the difference academic stress among the colleges. This value was observed to be less than the critical value of 3.03 given 2 and 256 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. This led to upholding the null hypothesis. It was concluded that Academic Stress does not significantly differ among respondents in the three Colleges.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the study revealed that academic stress significantly affects students academic performance, as measured by their CGPA. This therefore suggests that high levels of academic stress can lead to lower CGPA, while low levels of stress may be associated with better academic performance. Academic stress is a major stressor which affects the CGPA of business education students. The result of the present study negates the findings of Siraj et al. (2014) who explored the association between stress levels and the academic performances and demonstrated that respondents with a high and severe stress level were observed to have a higher cumulative grade point average. The medical students were found to be highly capable of managing their stress well and, thus, deny the adverse effect of stress on their academic performance. The findings however, supports the assertion of Sohail (2013) who conducted a study to determine the relationship of stress and academic

performance in first year medical students and to identify sources of stress, levels of stress and relevant coping strategies. The results also show that higher level of stress is associated with poor academic performance.

The study further revealed that there is a significant difference in stress management strategy adopted by the students based on their CGPA. There was a statistically significant difference revealed among all pairs of means, students with higher CGPA group of 3.5 to 4.5 reported the most effective stress management strategies, being highest mean, students with average CGPA group of 2.5 to 3.5 reported moderately effective stress management strategies, and the mean for the CGPA group of 1.5 to 2.5 being the lowest. This study supports the findings of Omosidi and Jamiu (2019), who found out that there was a positive significant relationship between relaxation management strategies, lifestyle management strategies and meditation management strategies with academic performance of undergraduates.

The study further revealed no significant difference in the amount of stress encountered by students in the three colleges of Education in Lagos. This might be due to the fact that they all offer the same number of courses. This suggests that students in all three colleges experience similar academic stress levels regardless of geographical location, institutional differences or even administrative structure. This might indicate that stressors affecting business education students are systemic or curriculum based rather than institution-specific. Though the environment seems to be different, and the lecturers different too, however, they all feel the same academic stress, probably because of the same workload, and limited time at their disposal. This therefore avers with the declaration of World Health Organisation as cited by Fink (2017) stress is a health epidemic experienced by all and sundry. The present study found that the ability to manage stress is important. If students can handle their stress, then their stress level will not matter. The important thing is to learn how to manage stress.

Conclusion

The study appraised academic stress, and academic performance of business education students in Colleges of Education in Lagos State. The present study evidenced the impact of academic stress on academic performance among college of education students in Lagos state. The study revealed that academic stress significantly impacts student's academic performance and that effective stress management strategies are linked to better academic outcomes. The study also established that students with higher academic achievement are more likely to adopt effective coping mechanisms than their peers with lower academic performance. Notably, students with higher CGPAs reported using more effective stress management strategies. However the study found no significant difference in the amount of stress encountered by students across the three colleges. Hence, it is imperative for educators, administrators, and policy makers to design and implement support programs that promote effective stress management and foster a conducive learning environment. Doing so will not only improve students' academic success but also enhance their overall well-being.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings.

1. Counseling centers should be instituted in the respective colleges of education and they should place more attention and support on counseling and training students to effectively manage and cope with stress.
2. Colleges of Education can develop stress management program tailored to students specific needs based on their CGPA.
3. Curriculum developers should review the business education course structure to ensure workload is balanced and not overwhelming. In addition, promoting peer mentoring and support groups and having a more engaging and flexible teaching methods will reduce academic stress.

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